

THE ROLE OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN FINANCING "GREEN ECONOMY" PROJECTS

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According to the analysis and results, it was found that the "Green" transition in the recent past is important for the most vulnerable sections of the population of Uzbekistan to climate change. Accordingly, the projected effects of climate change, including increased urban temperatures, frequent droughts, increased water scarcity, and increased threats of desertification and salinization, will affect life in the already impoverished regions of Uzbekistan. may disproportionately affect the level. For example, households in Uzbekistan spend a relatively high proportion of their income on food - in 2016 it was 47.3 percent [1].

Some economists see the green economy as an offshoot or subfield of the more established schools. According to economist D. Runnals' approach, the "green" economy is seen as a classical economy in which traditional land is generalized to natural capital and shares some common features with labor and physical capital (because natural capital assets such as rivers directly replace man-made assets such as canals clicks). Either it is viewed as Marxist economics, in which nature is a form of Lumpenproletariat, an exploitable base of inhuman workers that provide surplus value to the human economy, or a branch of neoclassical economics in which development costs life, etc. Developed countries maintain a stable ratio reflecting the balance of power, and have introduced it as a scientific hypothesis in their scientific literature that non-human life is very low [2].

According to the scientific research theories of one of the well-known economists of our republic, A. Vahabov, "green economy" is more practical in nature, unlike environmental economy or ecological economy. "Green economy" is not a field of scientific science, but mainly refers to real economic policy, concrete fields of activity (energy, innovation, agriculture, etc.). This difference can be observed in the expression of "green economy" not by the English words economics (economic theory or economic sciences such as environmental economics, ecological economics), but by the words economy (real economic activity) [3].

This is higher than the average of 38.6 percent in a representative sample of 92 developing countries [4] and puts the poor at risk of rising food prices.

Energy production and distribution is also not fair: almost half of Uzbekistan's population lives in rural areas, which face serious problems of power shortages and outages due to poor power distribution in remote areas, illegal use, and poor infrastructure [5].

Today, Uzbekistan understands well the unique opportunity to overcome the limits of growth under its current development model and to strengthen its economic competitiveness in the world market, which is becoming aware of the climate and ecology [6].

The country relies on the acceleration of structural reforms to create low-carbon and climate-resilient “green” cities based on Adaptive, Inclusive, Sustainable and Efficient (MIBS) use of natural resources, while creating new jobs in emerging sectors for its economy, people and planet. Steps are being taken to chart a path to a growth model [7].

According to statistics, Uzbekistan's “green” policy design shows that the loans allocated by commercial banks until April 1, 2023 for the country's greening processes are bearing fruit [8].

Table 1

Loans provided by commercial banks for the purchase of solar panels until April 1, 2023 [9]

№	Name of the bank	Loans allocated to business entities			Loans allocated to households		
		The number	billion soum	Power (kW)	The number	billio n soum	Powe r (kW)
	Total	91	160,3	12390	2704	67,3	6039
1	Uzmilliybank	6	81,4	655	1	0,03	3
2	Uzsanoatkurilish bank	4	25,6	7500	360	10,1	905
3	Asaka bank	1	11,4	1138	51	1,1	107
4	Agrobank	25	7,3	734	344	9,4	821
5	Ipoteka bank	4	12,5	55	139	3,1	278
6	Khalq banki	10	1,1	140	862	17,4	1619
7	Kishlok kurilish bank	4	1,1	56	205	5,3	504
8	Microcreditbank	10	4,5	467	723	19,8	1755
9	Turon bank	3	3,9	385	0	0,00	0
1	Aloka bank	4	1,8	176	0	0,00	0

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1 1	Khxamkorkbank	1	0,1	5	1	0,0	2
1 2	Ipak yuli bank	2	1,6	105	4	0,1	14
1 3	Capital bank	4	0,7	207	0	0,0	0
1 4	Davr bank	1	2,0	220	0	0,1	0
1 5	Asia alliance bank	7	3,6	71	14	1,0	31
1 6	Universalbank	1	0,3	20	0	0,00	0
1 7	Garant bank	4	1,6	156	0	0,00	0

According to the analytical data of Table 1, 160.3 bln. 91 in the amount of soums and 67.3 billion to households. 2704 solar panels worth 2704 soums were allocated, and loans were directed for the purchase of 2795 solar panels worth 227.6 soums in total [10].

As a result of the above scientific research, we were able to formulate a number of proposals and practical recommendations regarding the prospects of introducing the "green" economy in the practice of Uzbekistan [11]:

First, today the world population is more than 8 billion. There are UN forecasts that the world population will reach 9.7 billion in 2050. By 2050, the population of Uzbekistan is expected to reach 60 million. At the same time, it can be said that while the amount of resources is decreasing, the range of problems related to climate change continues to expand. As a result, the main problem of the economy and the scope of problems related to food security are expanding. Based on this, we believe that it is necessary to take immediate measures to reduce global emissions and support green, inclusive and sustainable development to reduce climate migration by up to 80 percent [12].

Secondly, the creation of a comfortable and quality living and working environment in cities is an important guarantee of social production and economic activity of the population [13]. Creating a favorable environment in cities is the mutual integration and matching of national planning and urban planning levels, these plans should be based on the principles of green economy,

which includes the changes observed in nature at the global level in recent years. , we believe that there must be directions aimed at mitigating the effects of climate change, encouraging digitization [14].

List of references:

1. Ugli J. U. P., Ugli A. M. I. Peculiarities of audit in commercial banks //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 6. – С. 477-481.
2. Хошимов Ж. ПРЯМЫЕ-СНИЖЕНИЕ СТРАНОВЫХ РИСКОВ ПРИ ПРИВЛЕЧЕНИИ ПРЯМЫХ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ИНВЕСТИЦИЙ //Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. S/2. – С. 149-155.
3. Kiyosov S. U. et al. Public Financing of The Health Care System: Problems and Opportunities //Journal of Intellectual Property and Human Rights. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 103-110.
4. Jo'rayev O. POSITION OF BANKS IN FINANCING INVESTMENT PROJECTS //Solution of social problems in management and economy. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 189-193.
5. Murtazaevich K. S. FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN ATTRACTING FOREIGN INVESTMENTS INTO THE NATIONAL ECONOMY //American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development. – 2023. – Т. 22. – С. 101-107.
6. Aminova N. U. Development of foreign economic activities in the republic of uzbekistan through attracting foreign investment //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research. – 2021. – Т. 10. – №. 8. – С. 216-221.
7. Khoshimov S. M. Foreign investment insurance in the global economy //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research. – 2021. – Т. 10. – №. 8. – С. 276-281.
8. Khoshimov, Jakhongir. "Overseas experience in the development of the life insurance industry." Молодые ученые 1.20 (2023): 65-69.
9. Murtazaevich K. S. Improving Foreign Investment Insurance in Uzbekistan //Eurasian Scientific Herald. – 2023. – Т. 20. – С. 68-79.
10. Qizi A. N. U. ISSUES OF FINANCING OF INVESTMENT PROJECTS ON THE BASIS OF SYNDICATE LOANING //Open Access Repository. – 2023. – Т. 10. – №. 12. – С. 8-14.
11. Abdullayevich N. I. The Impact of Attracting Foreign Direct Investment on Economic Development //Science Promotion. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 14-19.
12. Giyozovich K. I., Vokhidovich G. S. Issues Of Tourism Development In Uzbekistan //The Peerian Journal. – 2024. – Т. 26. – С. 7-12.

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13. Aminova N. U. Q., Zukhurova M. S. Q., Tulagankhujaeva I. S. Q. INVESTMENT PROCESS AND INVESTMENT POLICY //Science and Education. – 2021. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 219-225.
14. Saloxov S. “Yashil iqtisodiyot” ni joriy etish istiqbollari. – 2023.

